

ARTIFICIAL FEEDING OF THE BEE FAMILY

Kenjayeva Nozima Jobirovna

Student of the 2 nd year of the Biology direction of BuhSU

nozimakenjayeveva89@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6410114>

Abstract: In the Bukhara region, it is important to feed the bee family with natural, vitamin-rich feeds that accelerate the development of the family, for artificial breeding of queens in early spring in the presence of a shortage of pollen and nectar. Natural nutrients have a positive effect on the development of the bee family and create a solid basis for the artificial breeding of queen bees.

Key words: natural nutrients, sugar juice, sweet corn juice, wheatgrass juice, breeding of bees, control group, experimental group, queen bees, artificial breeding of bees, larvae, zootechnical indicators.

The nature of the territory of our republic differs from other republics in its character. The four seasons have their own special character and nature. The climate of the Bukhara region differs from other regions by its sharply continental climate. The summer season is very hot and dry, and the winter season is very dry and cold.

In such conditions, honey plants undergo many changes during the growing season, rich in nectar and pollen, which, in turn, affects regional beekeeping.

The fact that the warm climatic conditions of the Bukhara region are sharply very hot, and the variability is much slower than that of the flight activity of bees and the accumulation of honey, the sharp warming of the air and the abundance of unexpected precipitation completely prevent the separation of nectar from plants.

During this period, the development process of the bee family stops, the mother bee slows down the laying of eggs. As a result, the number of offspring of young bees in the family decreases.

It is very important to feed the bee family with natural vitamin nutrients rich in proteins, which accelerate the growth and development of the bee family, in addition, accelerate the development of the family, in order to grow queen bees artificially, during the period when plants do not have pollen in early spring. It is known that this natural nutrient has a positive effect on the development of the bee family, which artificially becomes a solid foundation for the cultivation of local bees.

For this purpose, in order to develop the bee family in early spring in the conditions of the Bukhara region in 2020, an experiment was set up, the cultivation of queen bees by artificial means, in addition to natural substances, wheat germ water was used for fertilizing. During the experiment, bee families were selected on the basis of zootechnical indicators and experimental groups consisting of three different, 8 bee families were formed on the basis of similarity. The first group was a control group, the other two were experimental groups. The first experimental group of both groups was fed with 50% sugar solution, 1 liter of sugar corn was added to 10 liters of sugar beet juice, and in the second experimental group, 1 liter of sugar beet juice was additionally given from March 28 to May 10, 2020, 300 mg every other day.

And in the control group, no additional feeding work was carried out. Control of bees in all groups was carried out on the basis of pre-established general methods.

It was found that the daily egg production of the mother bee increased by April 16 in the II experimental group by 15.5% compared with the control, and in the II experimental group - by 31.3%. Similarly, on May 10, these proportions increased by 12.9% and 32.3%. ($R > 0.999$). Various natural nutrients were used in the cultivation of local queen bees. For this purpose, two different groups of variants were used when growing local bees artificially. When breeding bees were given to their families to raise larvae, they were given two different types of nutrients.

And in the control group, only honey was used, which was in the framework, and 50% sugar juice. In the I experimental group, one liter of sweet corn juice was added to 50% liters of 10 liters of sugar juice, and in the II experimental group, water was added from a ratio of 10/1 with the addition of soybeans. Since early spring, when growing local bees artificially, in order to ensure the growth and development of the bee family, natural nutrients have been added to the composition of sugar juice containing bee feed. As a result of the adoption of larvae by local bees during the artificial breeding of queen bees increased by 18-22%, the weight of queen bees increased by 8-12 mg, it is noted that the daily laying of eggs reaches 2000 pcs.

On beekeeping farms, it is of great importance to use water from sugar corn and wheat shoot juice in addition to sugar juice with mineral and natural nutrients that stimulate families of growing bees for the purpose of artificial cultivation of queen bees.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. Сафарова З. Т., Фармонова О. С. К. МЕДОНОСНЫЕ РАСТЕНИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА //Scientific progress. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 1083-1084.
2. Азизова Н., Махмадияров О., Қўлдошева Ф., Тўраев О. Сунъий усулда она асалари етиштиришда сумалак сувини она асалари вазнига таъсири. Чорвачилик бўйича республика илмий-амалий конференция материаллари. Самарқанд, 2019, 82-84 бетлар.
3. Азизова Н., Махмадияров О., Қўлдошева Ф., Тўраев О. Майсали буғдой (сумалак) сувини асалари оиласи махсулдорлигини оширишга таъсири. Чорвачилик бўйича республика илмий-амалий конференция материаллари. Самарқанд, 2019, 79-81 бетлар.
4. Бойценюк Л.И., Малиновский Н.В., Новый прием увеличения массы маток и трутней. Ж. Пчеловодство, 2001, № 1, стр. 19-20.
5. Тўраев О., Дониёров С.Т., Азизова Н.А., Махмадияров О.А. Искусственных вывод маток на пасеках. Ипакчилик институти 90 йиллигига бағишланган материаллари тўплами. Тошкент, 2017, 290-293 бетлар.

